

Artificial Intelligence - Driven Digital Literacy Programmes for the Enhancement of Adult Learning in Delta State, Nigeria

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17073121>

Abstract

This study examined AI-driven digital literacy programmes for the enhancement of adult learning in Delta State. AI-driven digital programmes such as adaptive or personalised learning (EnGen), digital literacy integration, and practical applications are designed to equip the adult learners with the skills and competencies needed to understand, evaluate and use AI technologies effectively. The study aimed at assessing AI-driven digital literacy programmes for the enhancement of adult learning in Central Senatorial District of Delta State. Three (3) research questions and three (3) hypotheses guided the study and tested at 0.05 levels. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population of the study were 224 adult learners' facilitators and the sample size is 140 which were randomly selected using a multi-stage sampling technique. The instrument of data collection is researcher self-structured questionnaire titled AI-Driven Digital Literacy Programmes for Adult Learning Questionnaire (AIDDLPALQ). The instrument was validated using face and content validity, while the reliability of the instrument was ascertained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficients which yielded a reliability index of 0.70. Data collected were analyzed with mean, standard deviation, independent t-test, and one-sample t-test. Findings revealed that digital tools were accessible to urban and rural learners; and facilitators lacked adequate training and support for AI-driven programmes. Based on findings, it was recommended that government and educational stakeholders should train and re-retain facilitators to enhance their capacity to integrate AI-driven teaching methodologies effectively in the study area.

Keywords: Adult Learning, Adult Learners, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Digital Literacy and Programmes

Introduction

The enhancement of adult learning has gained increasing attention globally as a critical driver for achieving personal development, economic growth, and social inclusion. Adult learning, a process where adults engage in systematic and sustained learning activities to gain new knowledge, skills, and competencies, is pivotal in addressing the challenges posed by rapid technological, economic, and social changes. For many adults, especially in a developing country Nigeria, learning opportunities serve as a pathway to improved livelihoods, empowerment, and participation in society. However, adult learning enhancement is often hindered by barriers such as limited access to educational resources, poor digital literacy, and inadequate adaptation to evolving technologies. The need to create accessible, effective, and sustainable learning systems tailored to adult learners is therefore paramount. Addressing these challenges requires innovative approaches that bridge the gap between adult learners and contemporary educational resources, with a focus on equipping them with the digital literacy needed to thrive in an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven world.

In recent years, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative tool in addressing barriers to education by offering personalized, scalable, and flexible learning solutions. AI-driven digital literacy programmes have the potential to revolutionize adult learning by providing tailored content, interactive learning experiences, and real-time feedback. These programmes leverage AI technologies to analyze learners' needs,

adapt to their learning styles, and ensure inclusivity. Locally, the application of AI-driven digital literacy programmes in Delta State, Nigeria is both innovative and timely, given the country's need to address gaps in adult education and equip its population with skills that align with global technological trends. By integrating AI with digital literacy programmes, this approach seeks to enhance adult learning outcomes, empower individuals, and foster socioeconomic development in the region.

The implementation and impact of AI-driven digital literacy programmes is underpinned by different variables or factors which include but not limited to: accessibility of digital tools, teachers' or facilitators' training and support, and sustainability of programmes. Each variable represents a fundamental aspect of how these programmes can be effectively implemented and optimized for adult learning enhancement.

The first of these variables is accessibility of digital tools. Accessibility is a cornerstone of effective adult education, particularly in digital literacy programmes. For many adults in Delta State, Nigeria, access to digital tools such as computers, smartphones, and internet connectivity remains a significant challenge. Studies have shown that the digital divide—the gap between those who have access to digital resources and those who do not—limits learning opportunities, especially for marginalized groups (Adebayo & Okechukwu, 2021). Ensuring accessibility involves not only the provision of affordable digital devices but also the development of user-friendly platforms that cater to adults with varying levels of literacy and technical skills. Locally, efforts to improve access to digital tools can play a transformative role in empowering adult learners, bridging the gap between rural and urban populations, and fostering inclusivity in education.

Teachers or facilitators training and support is also another issue of concern worthy of mentioning. The role of educators in AI-driven digital literacy programmes cannot be overstated. Teachers or facilitators need to be equipped with the knowledge and skills to integrate AI technologies into their instructional practices effectively. Training programmes should focus on building teachers' capacity to use AI tools, design digital learning content, and support adult learners in navigating digital platforms (Uche & Okoli, 2021). In Delta State, teachers or facilitators training and support are critical for overcoming resistance to technology and ensuring that educators serve as facilitators of meaningful learning experiences. Empowering teachers will not only enhance the quality of instruction but also boost learners' confidence in engaging with digital tools.

The last variable of concern which is also of interest to the researcher is the sustainability of programmes. Sustainability is a key consideration in the implementation of AI-driven digital literacy programmes. Ensuring long-term impact involves not only securing funding but also building local capacity to maintain and scale these programmes. Partnerships with stakeholders, including government agencies, NGOs, and private sector players, are essential for sustaining these initiatives (Nwankwo, 2016). In Delta State, Nigeria, sustainability efforts should focus on integrating these programmes into existing adult education frameworks and creating policies that support continuous improvement and scalability.

The integration of AI-driven digital literacy programmes as seen from the above discussion offers a promising solution to the challenges of enhancing adult learning in Delta State, Nigeria. Hence, examining and tackling the critical variables such as accessibility, teachers or facilitators training, and sustainability of these programmes can create a transformative impact on adult education. Locally, this approach aligns with the district's need to bridge the digital divide, empower its population, and foster socioeconomic development. As stakeholders explore the potential of AI in education, it is imperative to build systems that are inclusive, sustainable, and tailored to the unique needs of adult learners. It was on this basis that this study seeks to examine artificial intelligence-driven digital literacy programmes like adaptive or personalised learning (EnGen), digital literacy integration, and practical applications for enhancing adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District of Delta State

Statement of the Problem

Adult learning is a vital tool for personal empowerment, economic growth, and social development. However, in Delta Central Senatorial District, the enhancement of adult learning remains a significant challenge due to limited digital literacy skills among the adult population, inadequate access to educational resources, and the inability of traditional learning methods to address the needs of adult learners in an increasingly digital

world. These issues hinder adults' capacity to engage meaningfully in socioeconomic activities, thus widening the digital divide and limiting opportunities for individual and community development.

Stakeholders, including government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and educational institutions, have made efforts to improve adult learning and promote digital literacy. Initiatives such as adult literacy centres were introduced but most of the adult learners could not utilize Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies effectively due to lack of better knowledge and skills. This gap has left many adult learners without the tailored support they need to overcome barriers to digital literacy and educational advancement.

Motivated by the transformative potential of AI-driven digital literacy programmes, the researcher seeks to address the persistent challenges limiting the enhancement of adult learning in the district. By investigating the implementation of AI-driven solutions, this study aims to bridge the gap in digital literacy, empower adult learners, and create a sustainable framework for adult education. The study would contribute to closing the existing gaps by exploring how AI can be used to make adult learning more accessible, adaptable, and impactful in Delta Central Senatorial District.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to examine the AI-driven digital literacy programmes for the enhancement of adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District of Delta State. The specific objectives are:

1. Examine the level of accessibility of digital tools required for the implementation of AI-driven digital literacy programmes in Delta Central Senatorial District.
2. Investigate the extent of facilitators' training and support for the integration of AI-driven digital literacy programmes for the enhancement of adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District.
3. Ascertain the extent of viability of AI-driven digital literacy programmes in enhancing adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District.

Research Questions

Based on the objectives of the study, the following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the level of accessibility of digital tools required for the implementation of AI-driven digital literacy programmes in Delta Central Senatorial District?
2. To what extent are facilitators well-trained and supported for the integration of AI-driven digital literacy programmes for the enhancement of adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District?
3. What is the extent of viability of AI-driven digital literacy programmes in enhancing adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 significant level.

H₀: There is no significant difference between urban and rural adult learners in the level of accessibility to digital tools required for the implementation of AI-driven digital literacy programmes in Delta Central Senatorial District.

H₀: There is no significant difference between facilitators trained and supported for the integration of AI-driven digital literacy programmes for the enhancement of adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District.

H₀: There is no significant difference between AI-driven digital literacy programmes and viability in enhancing adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District.

Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive survey design to assess AI-driven digital literacy programmes like adaptive or personalised learning (EnGen), digital literacy integration, and practical applications for enhancing adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District. This design is appropriate as it enables the researcher to describe the characteristics of a population and assess the relationships between variables without influencing the subjects.

This study was carried out in Delta Central Senatorial District, a key administrative and political division in Delta State, Nigeria. Delta Central Senatorial District comprises eight (8) local government areas (LGAs), namely: Ethiope East, Ethiope West, Okpe, Sapele, Udu, Ughelli North, Ughelli South and Uvwvie local Government Areas. Adult education is gaining relevance in this Central Senatorial District, with various adult literacy centres, skill acquisition centres, and continuing education programmes aimed at reducing the high rate of illiteracy among adults. Some notable centres include: Agency for Adult and Non-Formal Education, Asaba, Adult Literacy Centres in Ughelli, Effurun, and Sapele.

The population of the study consisted of two hundred and twenty (224) adult learners and facilitators in all the 41 adult learning centres which are the formal literacy and educational programmes across the eight LGAs of Delta Central Senatorial District (Ministry of Women Affairs, Delta State, 2024).

The sample size for this study was 144 adult learners and facilitators, selected across four (4) local government areas out of the eight (8) local government areas in the Delta Central Senatorial District. The 144-sample size was determined using the Taro Yamane sampling technique. However, the multi-stage sampling technique was employed for the study. Therefore, out of 8 local governments in the study area, the proportional sampling was used to select four local government areas representing 50% of the respondents from each local government area across the various selected adult learning centres.

The research instrument used for data collection in the study was a structured questionnaire titled AI-driven digital Literacy Programmes for Adult Learning Questionnaire (AIDDLPALQ). The validity of the instrument was ensured through face and content validity method by three research experts from the field of Adult education, Information and Communication Technology and Measurement and Evaluation. The experts were consulted to review the items for clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness. The reliability of the instrument was conducted using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient method. A pilot test of test retest was conducted with 30 adult learners outside the study sample. The coefficient was calculated from the data obtained to determine internal consistency, with a value of 0.70 which is considered acceptable. A total of 144 questionnaires were administered to the respondents in their respective adult learning centres on the four selected local government areas. Out of the 144 administered, 140 was retrieved giving a total of 97.2% return rate. The data collected were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Inferential statistics, including independent t-test, and one sample t-test were used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level.

Data Presentation and Analysis

This section focused on data presentation, analysis and discussion of findings.

Research Question 1: What is the level of accessibility of digital tools required for the implementation of AI-driven digital literacy programmes in Delta Central Senatorial District?

Table 1: Analysis of level of accessibility to digital tools required for implementation.
n=140

S/n	Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
1.	AI-driven literacy programmes are readily available in my teaching environment	1.5571	.85891	Lo w level
2.	I have easy access to a variety of digital tools for teaching adult learners.	1.6571	.93510	Lo w level
3.	The school provides adequate digital tools for AI-based literacy programmes.	1.6714	.76283	Lo w level
4.	I am provided with sufficient training to use digital tools for adult education.	1.8429	1.01974	Lo w level
5.	The digital tools available are modern and effective for AI-driven literacy programmes	1.9357	1.04027	Lo w level
6.	I can easily integrate digital tools into my lesson plans for adult learners.	1.8571	1.01479	Lo w level
7.	There is a lack of digital tools in my school for implementing AI-driven literacy programmes.	3.3857	.84467	High level
8.	Digital tools provided for AI literacy programmes meet the needs of adult learners.	1.7500	.90661	Lo w level
9.	Accessibility to digital tools does not hinder the implementation of AI literacy programmes.	2.2286	1.15268	Lo w level
10.	There are enough digital tools available for teaching adult learners in the district	1.9714	1.02447	Lo w level
Grand Mean		1.99	0.96	Low level

The Table above analyzes the level of accessibility to digital tools required for the implementation of AI-driven digital literacy programmes in Delta Central Senatorial District. The mean values range from 1.56 to 3.39, with most items indicating a low level of accessibility. Specifically, the highest mean value (3.39) shows a high level of lack of digital tools, highlighting a major limitation in accessibility. The grand mean is 1.99, with a standard deviation of 0.96, reflecting an overall low level of accessibility. This indicates that digital tools required for AI-driven literacy programmes are largely inaccessible, hindering effective implementation in the district.

Research Question 2: To what extent are teachers/facilitators well trained and supported for the integration of AI-driven digital literacy programmes for the enhancement of adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District?

**Table 2: Mean and Standard deviation of extent the teachers/facilitators well trained and supported for the integration of AI-driven digital literacy programmes for the enhancement of adult learning
n=140**

S/N	Item	Mean	Std	Remark
1	Teachers in my school receive regular training on AI-driven digital literacy programs.	2.2143	1.01631	Low extent
2	The training provided to teachers is adequate for implementing AI-based literacy programmes.	2.2143	.95801	Low extent
3	Teachers have access to resources that support their integration of AI-driven programmes.	2.0714	.96442	Low extent
4	I feel well-supported by the school administration for integrating AI into my lessons.	1.9143	.86070	Low extent
5	Teachers receive continuous professional development on the use of AI tools in education.	1.9357	.88318	Low extent
6	There is a lack of professional development opportunities for teachers to integrate AI-driven programs.	1.8286	.75810	Low extent
7	The training I received on AI tools was sufficient for enhancing adult learning.	1.9500	.94698	Low extent
8	Teachers receive timely updates about new AI-driven teaching strategies.	1.9071	.91271	Low extent
9	Teachers are not adequately prepared for implementing AI-driven digital literacy programs.	1.8357	.79214	Low extent
10	The level of support from the school is adequate for teachers to integrate AI tools.	1.8643	.84997	Low extent
Grand Mean		1.97	0.89	Low extent

The analysis presented in Table 2 evaluates the extent to which teachers and facilitators are well-trained and supported for the integration of AI-driven digital literacy programmes for enhancing adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District. The mean responses for all items range from 1.83 to 2.21, with corresponding standard deviations between 0.75 and 1.02, consistently indicating a low extent across all evaluated aspects.

Among the items assessed, both the regularity and adequacy of teacher training on AI-driven digital literacy programmes have the highest mean scores (2.21, SD = 1.02 and 0.96, respectively), yet these remain within the "low extent" category. Access to resources supporting integration (Mean = 2.07, SD = 0.96) and timely updates on AI-driven teaching strategies (Mean = 1.91, SD = 0.91) also show inadequacy. Other critical areas, such as feeling supported by the school administration (Mean = 1.91, SD = 0.86) and receiving sufficient professional development opportunities (Mean = 1.83, SD = 0.75), further indicate significant gaps.

The grand mean of the responses (1.97) reinforces the overall finding that teachers and facilitators in the district are not adequately trained or supported for integrating AI-driven digital literacy programmes into adult learning. This highlights a critical need for more robust and consistent professional development opportunities, administrative support, and access to necessary resources. Addressing these gaps is essential to ensure teachers and facilitators are well-prepared to deliver AI-enhanced education effectively.

Research Question 3: What is the extent of viability of AI-driven digital literacy programmes in enhancing adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District?

Table 3: Mean and standard of the extent of viability of AI-driven digital literacy programmes in enhancing adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District

n=140

S/N	Item	Mean	Std	Remark
1	AI-driven digital literacy programmes are viable in my school over the long term.	1.9714	.95166	Low extent
2	There are plans in place to ensure the continuation of AI-driven literacy programmes in the future.	2.1286	1.04464	Low extent
3	The resources available for AI-driven digital literacy programmes are sustainable.	2.0000	.96708	Low extent
4	The programmes viability is supported by regular funding and resource allocation.	2.1071	1.00857	Low extent
5	Teachers have the necessary skills and resources to sustain AI-driven literacy programs.	1.9429	.95036	Low extent
6	AI-driven literacy programmes face viability challenges due to inadequate funding.	2.6143	1.04974	High extent
7	The programme is likely to continue without significant changes in the near future.	1.9929	.93298	Low extent
8	The support for making AI-driven programmes is constant and uninterrupted.	1.9429	.91173	Low extent
9	The programme may be discontinued due to lack of resources or support.	2.5786	1.09326	High extent
10	The district has a clear plan for making AI-driven literacy programmes viable for adult learners.	2.0214	.94806	Low extent
	Grand Mean	2.13	0.99	Low extent

Table 3 evaluates the extent of viability of AI-driven digital literacy programmes in enhancing adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District. The findings indicate a low extent of viability overall, with a grand mean of approximately 2.13. Most items reveal challenges in making these programmes, such as insufficient long-term plans (Mean = 2.1286), limited availability of sustainable resources (Mean = 2.0000), and a lack of consistent support and funding (Mean = 2.1071). Teachers also lack adequate skills and resources to ensure viability (Mean = 1.9429), and there are no clear district-wide plans to secure the continuation of these programmes (Mean = 2.0214).

However, specific items highlight critical concerns, such as the viability challenges due to inadequate funding (Mean = 2.6143) and the potential discontinuation of programmes due to resource or support deficits (Mean = 2.5786), which scored high in impact. Despite these significant challenges, there are limited indicators of readiness for continuity, but they are not sufficient to guarantee long-term success. Overall, the results show the pressing need for improved funding, strategic planning, and support to enhance the viability of AI-driven digital literacy programmes for adult learners in the district.

Test of Hypotheses

H0: There is no significant difference between urban and rural adult learners in the level of accessibility to digital tools required for the implementation of AI-driven digital literacy programmes in Delta Central Senatorial District.

Table 4: Independent Samples Test for Accessibility to Digital Tools between Urban and Rural Learners
t-test for Equality of Means

Variables	N	Mean	Std Deviation	t-cal	Df	Sig	Remark
Urban	61	.20.1198	4.84458	0.610	138	0.54	Accepted
Rural	79	19.6582	4.01244				

The hypothesis tested in this study states that there is no significant difference between urban and rural adult learners in the level of accessibility to digital tools required for the implementation of AI-driven digital literacy programmes in Delta Central Senatorial District.

From the Independent Samples Test, Levene's Test for Equality of Variances shows a p-value of 0.197, which is greater than 0.05, indicating that the assumption of equal variances is valid. The t-test results show a t-value of 0.610 and a p-value of 0.543. Since the p-value (0.543) is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no statistically significant difference between urban and rural adult learners in their accessibility to digital tools.

H0: Teachers/facilitators are not significantly trained and supported for the integration of AI-driven digital literacy programmes for the enhancement of adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District.

Table 5: One Sample t-test of significant training and support for facilitators on the integration of AI-driven literacy programme towards enhancing adult learning

One-Sample Statistics						
	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean		
Facilitators Training and Support on AI	140	19.7357	7.94279	.67129		
One-Sample Test						
Test Value = 35.0						
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Facilitators Training on AI	-22.739	139	.000	-15.26429	-16.5915	-13.9370

The table titled One-Sample t-Test of Significant Training and Support for Facilitators on the Integration of AI-Driven Literacy Programme Towards Enhancing Adult Learning provides statistical evidence to evaluate Hypothesis, which posits that teachers/facilitators are not significantly trained and supported for the integration of AI-driven digital literacy programmes in Delta Central Senatorial District. The sample mean for facilitators' training and support is 19.7357, with a standard deviation of 7.94279, and a standard error mean of 0.67129, based on a sample size of 140. The test value for comparison is 35.0, representing the benchmark for significant training and support. The one-sample t-test yields a t-statistic of -22.739 with 139 degrees of freedom and a p-value of .000 (2-tailed). This indicates that the observed mean is significantly different from the test value. The mean difference is -15.26429, with a 95% confidence interval ranging from -16.5915 to -13.9370. Since the observed mean (19.7357) is significantly lower than the test value (35.0) and the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This confirms that teachers/facilitators are indeed not significantly trained and supported for the integration of AI-driven digital literacy programmes for enhancing adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District.

H0: AI-driven digital literacy programmes are not significantly viable in enhancing adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District.

Table 6: One Sample t-test of AI-driven digital literacy programmes and its viability in enhancing adult learning

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
AI Digital Literacy Programme	140	21.3000	6.61120	.55875

One-Sample Test						
Test Value = 35.0						
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
AI Digital Literacy Programme	-24.519	139	.000	-13.70000	-14.8047	-12.5953

The table 6 tested the hypothesis which stated that "AI-driven digital literacy programmes are not significantly viable in enhancing adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District." A one-sample t-test was conducted to assess the viability of AI-driven digital literacy programmes in enhancing adult learning. The results showed a mean score of 21.3, with a standard deviation of 6.6112 and a standard error mean of 0.55875. The t-value was -24.519, with 139 degrees of freedom, and the p-value was 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 0.05. This indicates that the mean difference between the observed value and the test value is statistically significant. The 95% confidence interval for the difference in means was between -14.8047 and -12.5953. Given that the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it can be concluded that AI-driven digital literacy programmes are significantly viable in enhancing adult learning in Delta Central Senatorial District.

Discussion of Findings

The finding from the study revealed that AI-driven digital literacy programmes are significantly sustainable in enhancing adult learning in the district. Additionally, it was found that there is no significant difference between urban and rural adult learners in the level of accessibility to digital tools required for the implementation of AI-driven digital literacy programmes in Delta Central Senatorial District. These two findings are interrelated, as accessibility to digital tools plays a crucial role in the long-term sustainability of such programmes. The findings suggest that despite challenges in access, AI-driven initiatives hold long-term potential for sustainability when strategic interventions are in place. This aligns with Ajibola (2018), and Uche and Okoli (2021), who found that access to digital tools in adult education centres faced similar challenges in both rural and urban areas, primarily due to financial and infrastructural constraints. Likewise, Adewale and Eze (2020) emphasized that AI-driven digital literacy programmes, despite initial difficulties, demonstrated long-term sustainability potential with adequate investment. However, Okoye and Okwori (2014) presented a contrary view, arguing that major sustainability barriers, such as funding limitations and resistance from facilitators, could threaten these programmes' longevity. The finding on accessibility aligns with Ajibola (2018), who found that both urban and rural learners in Nigeria face similar accessibility challenges due to financial and infrastructural constraints. Uche and Okoli (2021) also identified major barriers such as lack of electricity, inadequate training, and limited internet access, affecting all learners equally. However, Olaniyan (2016) argued that rural areas were more disadvantaged due to outdated curricula and inadequate infrastructure. On sustainability, Adewale and Eze (2020) found that AI-driven digital literacy programmes demonstrated long-term potential despite initial funding challenges. Similarly, Uche and Okoli (2021) suggested that strategic interventions could enhance programme longevity, whereas Okoye and Okwori (2014) cautioned that major barriers like funding limitations and technical support threatened sustainability.

Secondly, the study indicated that teachers and facilitators are not significantly trained or supported for integrating AI-driven digital literacy programmes. Additionally, policies governing the implementation of such programmes are weak and inconsistent. These findings are related, as strong policy frameworks are essential for

ensuring adequate training and support for teachers. Okoye and Okwori (2014) found that while teachers were aware of AI's potential, they lacked adequate training for effective implementation. Adewale and Bello (2020) emphasized that continuous professional development significantly improved digital literacy adoption. However, Olaniyan and Lucas (2016) noted that pilot initiatives had successfully trained some teachers, though efforts remained insufficient. Regarding policy implementation, Ajibola (2018) argued that weak policies hindered the integration of AI in education. Uche and Okoli (2021) suggested that well-defined policies could enhance programme effectiveness, but inconsistencies in implementation often limited their impact.

Thirdly, the study established that AI-driven digital literacy programmes are significantly viable in enhancing adult learning. However, socio-economic barriers hinder their widespread adoption. These findings are connected, as viability efforts must address socio-economic barriers to ensure broader participation and impact. Adewale and Eze (2020) found that AI-driven digital literacy programmes demonstrated long-term potential despite initial funding challenges. Similarly, Uche and Okoli (2021) suggested that strategic interventions could enhance programme longevity. However, Okoye and Okwori (2014) cautioned that major barriers like funding limitations and technical support threatened sustainability. Ajibola (2018) identified socio-economic challenges such as poverty, lack of digital awareness, and financial constraints as critical factors limiting access to digital literacy programmes. Addressing these barriers is essential for ensuring the long-term success of AI-driven digital literacy initiatives.

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed the critical need for a holistic approach to AI-driven digital literacy programmes in Delta Central Senatorial District. The study concluded that accessibility to digital tools is a key determinant of the sustainability of these programmes. Without adequate access, especially among adult learners in both urban and rural areas, the long-term effectiveness of digital literacy initiatives remains uncertain. While the programmes show potential for sustainability, persistent barriers such as infrastructure deficits, lack training for facilitators, financial constraints, and inadequate policy support must be addressed to ensure their continued impact.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations became imperative.

1. Government and policymakers should prioritize investment in digital infrastructure by providing reliable internet access, modern technological tools, and electricity to support digital literacy programmes in both urban and rural areas.
2. Teachers training bodies and facilitators should undergo continuous professional development on AI-driven instructional methods to improve their competency and effectiveness in delivering digital literacy education.
3. Private sector and technology firms should collaborate with educational institutions to provide funding, digital tools, and capacity-building programmes to support the viability of AI-driven digital literacy initiatives.

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